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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF GEMCITABINE
NIOSOMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM****G. Harikiriti Varma*¹, Vijaya Kuchana², E. Akshaya¹, E. Nandulal¹, E. Ankitha¹,
G. Sai charan¹, G. Jyoshna¹**¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Teegala Krishna Reddy College of Pharmacy, Medbowli,
Meerpet, Saroornagar, Hyderabad.²Principal and Professor, Teegala Krishna Reddy College of Pharmacy, Medbowli, Meerpet,
Saroornagar, Hyderabad.**Abstract:**

The present study was focused on formulating and evaluating Gemcitabine containing niosomes formulation for invitro studies. Niosomal formulations were prepared by using different ratio of surfactant (Tween 40 and Span 80) and cholesterol by thin film hydration method and were evaluated for in vitro characteristics, stability studies. Span 80 containing niosomal formulation displayed highest entrapment efficiency with desired particle size. SEM analyses showed that niosomal formulation was spherical in shape. Niosomes containing Span 80 displayed higher percentage of drug release after 8h as compared to other formulations. F-4 formulation was found to be stable at the end of the study on storage condition. The present study suggested that niosomal formulations provide sustained and prolonged delivery of drug with enhance bioavailability.

Keywords: Niosomes, Gemcitabine, bioavailability, thin film hydration technique, in vitro drug release studies.

Corresponding author:**G. Harikiriti Varma,**

Assistant professor,

Department of Pharmaceutics,

Teegala Krishna Reddy College of Pharmacy,

Medbowli, Meerpet, Saroornagar, Hyderabad- 500097

Mail-ID: harikiriti@gmali .com**Mobile Number:** 9133333429.

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INTRODUCTION:

A novel drug delivery system is an umbrella term used to describe cutting-edge techniques and tools created to boost the therapeutic effectiveness of medications while reducing potential negative effects while improving patient compliance.¹ Niosomes are formed of bilayer spherical vesicles, which consist of nonionic surfactants and cholesterol in an aqueous medium, while liposomes are bilayer vesicles made by phospholipids enclosing an aqueous medium.² Both have efficiency in encapsulating hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs at the aqueous layer and the lipid bilayer, respectively. They are more stable than liposomes and have the ability to encapsulate hydrophilic and lipophilic molecules with biological activity. Niosomes have an amphiphilic bilayer structure with a polar part on the surface and a non-polar zone inside and are made up of non-ionic surfactants and cholesterol.³

The application of niosomal technology is widely varied and can be used to treat a number of diseases. One of the most useful aspects of niosomes is their ability to target vaccines and drugs to the reticulo-endothelial system. The reticulo-endothelial system (RES) preferentially takes up niosomal vesicles. The uptake of niosomes is controlled by circulating serum factors called opsonins, which mark the niosomes for clearance^[4] while delivering the cargo to the antigen presenting cells. The application of niosomal technology is widely varied and can be used to treat a number of diseases. One of the most useful aspects of niosomes is their ability to target vaccines and drugs to the reticulo-endothelial system. The reticulo-endothelial system (RES) preferentially takes up niosomal vesicles. The uptake of niosomes is controlled by circulating serum factors called opsonins, which mark the niosomes for clearance^[4] while delivering the cargo to the antigen presenting cells.

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deoxycytidine, dFdC) is a cytidine analogue that is widely used in the treatment of pancreatic cancer.⁶ In this study, optimized the formulation of gemcitabine niosomes to enhance the anti-tumor activity of gemcitabine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**MATERIALS**

Gemcitabine procured from Hetero Labs, HYD. Cholesterol, Tween 40 and Span 80 was obtained from Synpharma Research Labs, Hyderabad. Other chemicals and the reagents used were of analytical grade.

METHODOLOGY**Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) study**

FTIR is a useful technique to check and confirm any interaction that may occur between excipients and drug. The FTIR spectra of drug, excipients, briefly, solid sample (1 mg) along with 100 mg dried potassium bromide was compressed into a disc. The sample were place onto NaCl or KBr aperture plate and sandwiched it under another aperture plate, such that no gas bubbles were trapped. The sample allowed formation of a thin liquid membrane between the two aperture plates. Thereafter, sample was scanned for absorbance over the range from 4000 to 400 (cm⁻¹) wave numbers. The obtained spectrum was then compared with standard group frequencies of Gemcitabine.⁷

Preparation of Niosomes

Gemcitabine niosomes were prepared using thin film-hydration method. Accurately weighed quantities of the surfactant (Span 80 and Tween 80) and cholesterol in different Ratios in around- bottom flask. Afterwards, Gemcitabine dissolved in 5ml of chloroform: methanol mixture (2:1) was added to the lipid solution. The organic solvents were removed under vacuum in a rotary evaporator at 40° C for 20min to form a thin film on the wall of the flask, and kept in a desiccator under vacuum for 2 h to ensure total removal of trace solvents. After removal of the last trace of organic solvents, hydration of the surfactant film was carried out using 10mL of distilled water at 55°C. The resulting niosomal suspension was mechanically shaken for 1 h using a horizontal mechanical shaking water bath at 55 ° C. Then, the vesicle suspension was sonicated in 3 cycles' of 1min "on" and 1min "off" leading to the formation of multi lamellar niosomes. The niosomal suspension was left to mature overnight at 4 ° C and stored at refrigerator temperature for further studies.⁸

Table-1: Composition of Niosomal Gemcitabine (F1 to F4)

S. No.	Ingredients (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Gemcitabine	1000	1000	1000	1000
2	Cholesterol	1000	1000	1000	1000
3	Tween 40	5	10	-	-
4	Span 80	-	-	5	10
5	Methanol	10	10	10	10
6	Chloroform	10	10	10	10

Evaluation of Niosomes

Particle size:

Size and size distribution studies were done for niosomes prepared from Niosomes hydration. The Niosomes (100 mg) was hydrated in a small glass test tube using 10 ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer solution. The dispersion was observed under optical microscope at 40X magnification. Similarly, size was noted for niosomes formed spontaneously from Niosomes after hydration without agitation in a cavity slide.⁹

Zeta-potential:

The sample was diluted with distilled water (1:100 (V/V)) and zeta potential was determined using Malvern zetasizer (Nano ZS, Malvern Instruments, United Kingdom). Measurement was based on the electrophoretic mobility of the particles, which was converted to the zeta potential by inbuilt software based on the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski equation.¹⁰

Vesicle physical analysis

The shape, surface characteristics, and size of the niosomes were observed by scanning electron microscopy. Once again, 0.2 g of the Niosomes in a glass tube was diluted with 10 ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. The niosomes were mounted on an aluminium stub using double-sided adhesive carbon tape. Then the vesicles were sputter-coated with gold palladium (Au/Pd) using a vacuum evaporator (Edwards) and examined using a scanning electron microscope (Hitachi 3700N, Germany) equipped with a digital camera, at 10 kV accelerating voltage.¹¹

Entrapment efficiency

To 0.2 g of Niosomes, weighed in a glass tube, 10 ml phosphate buffer pH 7.4 were added. The aqueous suspension was then sonicated. Niosomes containing Gemcitabine were separated from untrapped drug by centrifugation at 9000rpm for 45 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was recovered and assayed spectrophotometrically using UV spectrophotometer (UV-1800 Shimadzu, Japan), at 250 nm.¹²

The encapsulation percentage of drug (EP) was calculated by the following equation

$$EP = [(C_t - C_r) / C_t] * 100$$

Where,

C_t, concentration of total Gemcitabine, C_r, concentration of free Gemcitabine.

In vitro drug release Study

In vitro release studies were carried out using unjacketed vertical franz diffusion cells with a diffusional surface area of 6.154 cm² and 20 mL of receptor cell volume. Prior to the study, the dialysis membrane was soaked in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 Formulation equivalent to 5mg of Gemcitabine was placed in the donor compartment. The receptor compartment consisting of PB pH 7.4 was maintained at 37±2°C under constant stirring up to 8 hrs. The donor chamber and the sampling port were covered with lid to prevent evaporation during the study. Aliquots of 5 mL were withdrawn periodically at different time intervals and replaced with equal volume to maintain constant receptor phase volume. At the end of the study, the samples were suitably diluted and the amount of drug was determined spectrophotometrically at 250 nm.¹³

Kinetics of drug release studies

The quantitative elucidation of the values obtained in the dissolution study is facilitated by the usage of a generic equation that mathematically translates the diffusion curve in function of some parameters related to the Niosomes. For understanding the mechanism of drug release and release rate kinetics of the drug from dosage form, the In vitro drug dissolution data of optimized formulations obtained was fitted to various mathematical models such as zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix and Korsmeyer-Peppas models.¹⁴

Zero order kinetics

Drug dissolution from pharmaceutical dosage forms that do not disaggregate and release the drug slowly can be represented by the following equation:

$$Q_0 - Q_t = K_0t$$

Arrangement of equation yields: $Q_t = Q_0 + K_0t$

Where Q_t is the amount of drug dissolved in time t,

Q₀ is the initial amount of drug in the solution (most times, Q₀ = 0)

and K_0 is the zero-order release constant expressed in units of concentration/time.

To study the release kinetics, data obtained from in vitro drug release studies were plotted as cumulative amount of drug released versus time.

First order Kinetics

The equation for first order release is given below

$$\text{Log } Q_t = \text{log } Q_0 + K_1 t / 2.303$$

Where Q_t is the amount of drug released in time t ,

Q_0 is the initial amount of drug in the solution

and K_1 is the first order release constant.

A graph of the decimal logarithm of the released amount of drug versus time will be linear. Niosomes following this diffusion profile release the drug in a way that is proportional to the amount of drug remaining in its interior, in such way, that the amount of drug released by unit of time diminishes.

Higuchi model

Higuchi described drug release as a diffusion process based on the Fick's law, square root time dependent. The simplified Higuchi equation is represented as

$$Q_t = K t^{1/2}$$

Where Q_t = amount of drug released in time t ,

K = Higuchi's constant

A linear relationship between amount of drug released (Q_0 versus square root of time ($t^{1/2}$) is observed if the drug release from the Niosomes is diffusion controlled.

Korsmeyer-Peppas model

This mathematical model, also known as the Power Law, has been used, very frequently; to describe the drug release from several different pharmaceutical modified release dosage forms. The Korsmeyer-Peppas model relates drug release exponentially to time. It is described by the following equation

$$M_t/M_\infty = a t^n$$

Where 'a' is a constant incorporating structural and geometric characteristics of Nano emulsion, 'n' is the release exponent, indicative of the drug release mechanism, and the function of 't' is M_t/M_∞ (fractional release of drug).

Stability Studies¹⁵

The formulations stored in glass vials covered with aluminium foil were kept at room temperature and in refrigerator (4°C) for a period of 90 days. At definite time intervals (10, 20, and 30 days), samples were withdrawn and hydrated with phosphate-buffered saline (pH 7.4) and observed for any sign of drug crystallization under optical microscope. Furthermore, the samples were also evaluated for particle size and percent retention of Gemcitabine.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Drug - excipient compatibility studies (FT-IR)

Using the FTIR peak matching approach, the compatibility of the medicine with the chosen polymer and other excipients was assessed. The drug-Excipients mixture showed no peaks that appeared or vanished, indicating that there was no chemical interaction between the medication, lipids and other molecules.

Fig-1: FTIR Studies of Gemcitabine

SHIMADZU

Fig-2: FTIR Studies of physical mixture of drug and excipients

EVALUATION PARAMETERS:

Entrapment Efficiency:

Table-2: Drug entrapment efficiency of all formulation

F.no	Drug entrapment efficiency
F1	82.15
F2	80.28
F3	83.14
F4	85.22

The formulate niosomes formulation's entrapment efficiency was in the range of 80.28-85.22%. The % EE of the prepared optimized formulation was found to be 85.22%.

Fig-3: Drug entrapment efficiency of all formulation

Determination of Vesicle morphology and Size

The morphology of the prepared diverse types of nanoparticles was found to be virtually spherical in shape and have a rough surface, as illustrated in SEM photomicrographs of the nanoparticles.

Fig-4: SEM analysis of Optimized niosomes

Evaluation Studies of particle size and Zeta potential Niosomes**Particle size**

Fig-5: Particle size analysis of Optimized niosomes

Zeta potential

Fig-6: Zeta potential analysis of Optimized niosomes

The ZP or change in the surface of colloidal particles in niosomes was studied to determine the charge on the particles to avoid agglomeration. Figure indicates the ZP of the optimized formulation as -35 mV.

Tble-3: Evaluation Studies of particle size and Zeta potential Niosomes

F. No	Particle size (nm)	Zeta potential
F1	146	-37
F2	141	-39
F3	135	-35
F4	155	-36

The mean particle size of optimized niosomes was found to be 155 nm.

***In vitro* drug release studies:**

Table-4: *In vitro* drug release profiles of Gemcitabine niosomes (F1-F6)

Time (hrs.)	% Cumulative drug released			
	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
1	15.68	17.85	16.57	19.68
2	28.93	27.64	28.93	24.20
3	35.81	34.50	38.64	37.96
4	43.69	46.38	48.50	47.82
5	51.46	55.34	58.46	54.50
6	68.90	67.14	68.12	67.98
7	76.68	79.82	80.10	82.39
8	91.56	94.52	93.56	96.72

Fig-7: Drug release of (F1-F4) formulations

The drug release studies of all formulations of Gemcitabine were conducted by means of Franz diffusion cell apparatus for a time period of 8 hrs. From the drug release studies as depicted in Figure, the results showed that 4th formulation showed maximum drug release rate of 96.72% within 8 hrs.

Drug release kinetics

All the 6 formulation of prepared Gemcitabine niosomes were subjected to in vitro release studies these studies were carried out using diffusion apparatus.

Zero order kinetics

The results obtaining in vitro release studies were plotted in different model of data treatment as follows:

1. Cumulative percent drug released vs. time (zero order rate kinetics)
2. Log cumulative percent drug retained vs. time (First Order rate Kinetics)
3. Cumulative percent drug released vs. square root of time (Higuchi's Classical Diffusion Equation)
4. Log of cumulative % release Vs log time (Peppas Exponential Equation)

Fig-8: Zero order kinetics of optimized formulation

First order kinetics**Fig-11: Korsmeyer peppas of optimized formulation**

The values of in vitro release were attempted to fit into various mathematical models. Plots of zero order, first order, Higuchi matrix and Peppas.

Regression values are higher with Zero order release kinetics. Therefore, all the Gemcitabine niosomes follows Zero order release kinetics.

The table indicates that r^2 values are higher for Higuchi's model compared for all the niosomes. Hence Gemcitabine release from all the niosomes followed diffusion rate-controlled mechanism.

Stability studies:

Optimized formulations F4 was selected for accelerated stability studies as per ICH guidelines. The Niosomes were observed for drug release for a period of three months.

Table-5: Stability studies of optimized formulations at 40 ± 2 °C and $75 \pm 5\%$ RH for 3 months

Formulation Code	Initial	1 st Month	2 nd Month	3 rd Month	Limits as per Specifications
F-4	96.72	95.86	94.58	93.79	Not less than 85 %
F-4	96.72	95.81	94.72	93.55	Not less than 85 %
F-4	96.72	95.74	94.46	93.28	Not less than 85 %

CONCLUSION:

The goal of the current formulation study on Gemcitabine is to create a niosomal drug delivery system and assess how well it functions in vitro. Different proportions of cholesterol and surfactant were used to create the formulations. High entrapment efficiency is regarded as the ideal or best niosome formulation. This study discovered that the ratio of cholesterol to surfactant affected entrapment efficiency. Formulations were discovered to guarantee the drug's good oral bioavailability. The niosomes were seen to be smooth-surfaced, spherical vesicles. The highest entrapment efficiency was demonstrated by Formulation F4. These facts lead to the conclusion that niosomes may be a promising method for increasing Gemcitabine bioavailability.

REFERENCES:

1. Lordi, N.G. Sustained release dosage forms. In: Lachman, L., Lieberman, H.A. and Kanig, J.L. (eds.) The theory and practice of industrial pharmacy, 3rd edn (Indian edn). Varghese Publishing House, Bombay, 1987; 430–456.
2. Ertekin Z., Bayindir Z., Yuksel N. Stability Studies on Piroxicam Encapsulated Niosomes. *Curr Drug Deliv.* 2015; 12:192–199.
3. Saraf S., Ankit J., Tiwari A., Verma A., Pandaa P.K., Jain S.K. Advances in liposomal drug delivery to cancer: An overview. *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol.* 2020; 56:101549.
4. Weissman G, Bloomgarden D, Kaplan R, Cohen C, Hoffstein S, Collins T, et al. A general method for the introduction of enzymes, by means of immunoglobulin-coated liposomes, into lysosomes of deficient cells. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 1975;72:88-92
5. E. Mini, Cellular pharmacology of gemcitabine, *Ann. Oncol.* (2006)
6. Mazayen Z.M., Ghoneim A.M., Elbatany R.S., Basalious E.B., Bendas E.R. Pharmaceutical nanotechnology: From the bench to the market. *Future J. Pharm. Sci.* 2022;8:12.
7. Sahani S., Sharma Y.C. Advancements in applications of nanotechnology in global food industry. *Food Chem.* 2021;342:128318.
8. Thatyana M., Dube N.P., Kemboi D., Manicum A.-L.E., Mokgalaka-Fleischmann N.S., Tembu J.V. Advances in Phytonanotechnology: A Plant-Mediated Green Synthesis of Metal Nanoparticles Using Phyllanthus Plant Extracts and Their Antimicrobial and Anticancer Applications. *Nanomaterials.* 2023;13:2616.
9. Bayda S., Adeel M., Tuccinardi T., Cordani M., Rizzolio F. The History of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology: From Chemical–Physical Applications to Nanomedicine. *Molecules.* 2020;25:112.
10. Soni R.A., Rizwan M.A., Singh S. Opportunities and potential of green chemistry in nanotechnology. *Nanotechnol. Environ. Eng.* 2022;7:661–673.

11. Manosroi A, Wongtrakul P, Manosroi J, Sakai H, Sugawara F, Yuasa M, et al. Characterization of vesicles prepared with various non-ionic surfactants mixed with cholesterol. *Colloids Surf B*. 2003;30:129–38.
12. Balasubramaniam A, Kumar VA, Pillai KS. Formulation and in-vivo evaluation of niosome encapsulated daunorubicin hydrochloride. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm*. 2002;28:1181–93.
13. Yoshioka T, Sternberg B, Florence AT. Preparation and properties of vesicles (niosomes) of sorbitan monoesters (Span 20, 40, 60, and 80) and a sorbitan triester (Span 85) *Int J Pharm*. 1994;105:1–6.
14. Karki R, Mamatha GC, Subramanya G, Udupa N. Preparation, characterization and tissue disposition of niosomes containing isoniazid. *Rasayan J Chem*. 2008;1:224–7.
15. Hunter CA, Dolan TF, Coombs GH, Baillie AJ. Vesicular system (niosomes and liposomes) for delivery of sodium stibogluconate in experimental murine visceral leishmaniasis. *J Pharm Pharmacol*. 1988;40:161–5.